

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ONOMATOPOEIA IN LINGUISTIC: FROM EXAMPLES TO CROSS-CULTURAL DIFFERENCES

Avilova Aziza Nabijon qizi

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

Abstract: This article is devoted to the role and importance of onomatopoeia in linguistics. This article explains onomatopoeia deeply with examples, how it developed, its place in early language acquisition, cross-cultural differences and most importantly how it plays a significant role in linguistics.

Keywords: onomatopoeia, direct and indirect onomatopoeia, cross-cultural, phonological context, phonetic, repetitive.

Onomatopoeia plays crucial role in linguistics. Firstly, what is onomatopoeia itself? Actually, Onomatopoeia is a use of words or combinations of words whose sounds produce an imitation of natural sound. As everything has its own division and subdivisions according to similar aspects and various characteristics, there are two varieties of onomatopoeia: direct and indirect. Direct onomatopoeia is contained in words that imitate natural sounds, as ding-dang, bang, cuckoo, mew, ping-pong and the like. These words have different degrees of imitative quality. Onomatopoeia words can be used in a transferred meaning, as for instance, ding-dong, which represents the sound of bell's rung continuously. E.g.: ding-dong struggle. More examples of such variety of onomatopoeia are the following. E.g.: to croak - the direct meaning is to make a deep harsh sound (about frogs and ravens), but in its transferred meaning it denotes a hoarse human voice. Its contextual meaning may be: to protest dismally, to predict evil ("каркать" in Russian). Note the following example: if that child doesn't stop whining, I'll drown it. In this sentence "whining" is used as an onomatopoeic word and means "long-drawn complaining cry or high-pitched sound made by a miserable dog (uzbek: ФИНГШИМОК).

Indirect onomatopoeia is a combination of sounds the aim of which is to make the sound of the utterance echo of its sense. It is sometimes called "echo-writing". E.g.: "And the silken, sad, uncertain rustling of each purple curtain". (E. A. Poe) Here repetition of the sound [s] produces the sound of the rustling of the curtain.

Onomatopoeic words are divided into the following groups: 1. Words denoting the sounds of movements: bang, boom, rustle, hum, crash, whip. 2. Words denoting sounds appearing in the process of communication: babble, giggle, grumble, murmur, whisper. 3. Sounds of animals, birds, insects: huzz, crackle, crow, hiss, moo, mew, purr, roar. 4. The sound of water: splash. 5. The sound of metallic things: clinc, tinkle etc.

Literature analysis: Onomatopoeia is the use or creation of a word that phonetically imitates, resembles, or suggests the sound that it describes. Such a word itself is also called an onomatopoeia. Common onomatopoeias include animal noises such as oink, meow (or miaow), roar, and chirp. Onomatopoeia can differ between languages: it conforms to some extent to the broader linguistics,

hence the sound of a clock may be expressed as tick tock in The English term comes from the Ancient Greek compound onomatopoeia, 'name-making', composed of onomato- 'name' and -toeia 'making'. Thus, words that imitate sounds can be said to be onomatopoeic or onomatopoeic.

Some other very common English-language examples are hiccup, zoom, bang, beep, moo, and splash. Machines and their sounds are also often described with onomatopoeia: honk or beep-beep for the horn of an automobile, and vroom or brum for the engine. In speaking of a mishap involving an audible arcing of electricity, the word zap is often used (and its use has been extended to describe non-auditory effects of interference).

Human sounds sometimes provide instances of onomatopoeia, as when mwah is used to represent a kiss. For animal sounds, words like quack (duck), moo (cow), bark or woof (dog), roar(lion), meow/miaow or purr(cat), cluck (chicken) and baa (sheep) are typically used in English (both as nouns and as verbs).

In linguistics, onomatopoeia is described as the connection, or symbolism, of a sound that is interpreted and reproduced within the context of a language, usually out of mimicry of a sound. It is a figure of speech, in a sense. Considered a vague term on its own, there are a few varying defining factors in classifying onomatopoeia. In one manner, it is defined simply as the imitation of some kind of non-vocal sound using the vocal sounds of a language, like the hum of a bee being imitated with a "buzz" sound. In another sense, it is described as the phenomena of making a new word entirely.

Onomatopoeia works in the sense of symbolizing an idea in a phonological context, not necessarily constituting a direct meaningful word in the process. The symbolic properties of a sound in a word, or a phoneme, is related to a sound in an environment, and are restricted in part by a language's own phonetic inventory, hence why many languages can have distinct onomatopoeia for the same natural sound. Depending on a language's connection to a sound's meaning, that language's onomatopoeia inventory can differ proportionally. For example, a language like English generally holds little symbolic representation when it comes to sounds, which is the reason English tends to have a smaller representation of sound mimicry than a language like Japanese that overall has a much higher amount of symbolism related to the sounds of the language.

In ancient Greek philosophy, onomatopoeia was used as evidence for how natural a language was: it was theorized that language itself was derived from natural sounds in the world around us. Symbolism in sounds was seen as deriving from this. Some linguists hold that onomatopoeia may have been the first form of human language.

When first exposed to sound and communication, humans are biologically inclined to mimic the sounds they hear, whether they are actual pieces of language or other natural sounds. Early on in development, an infant will vary his/her utterances between sounds that are well established within the phonetic range of the language(s) most heavily spoken in their environment, which may be called "tame" onomatopoeia, and the full range of sounds that the vocal tract can produce, or "wild" onomatopoeia. As one begins to acquire one's first language, the proportion of "wild" onomatopoeia reduces in favor of sounds which are congruent with those of the language they are acquiring .

During the native language acquisition period, it has been documented that infants may react strongly to the more wild-speech features to which they are exposed, compared to more tame and familiar speech features. But the results of such tests are inconclusive.

In the context of language acquisition, sound symbolism has been shown to play an important role. The association of foreign words to subjects and how they relate to general objects, such as the

association of the words takete and baluma with either a round or angular shape, has been tested to see how languages symbolize sounds.

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